

ROLE OF ICT FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Suleiman, Muhammad Muhammad^{1*}

Surajo, Amimu Zubairu²

Matinja, Zakari Idris³

^{1,2} Kano State Polytechnic, Kano State, Nigeria

³ Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria

*corresponding author: muhddkd@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

A large proportion of young graduates in most African countries exist without clear job prospects. Self-employment may be one potential answer to this issue. On the other side, such an approach necessitates the production of entrepreneurship skills. ICT should be seen as an ideal tool to accelerate the development process of Nigeria's entrepreneurship programs. This article attempted to address the roles of ICT in an Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria's entrepreneurial growth. It has also been discovered that restricting factors such as regular power loss, shortage of skilled technicians/repairers, availability of insurance, emergencies, and uncertainty are barriers that any potential entrepreneur will overcome. Among other issues, the article suggests that the government subsidizes these ICT resources imports to minimize the expense of such tools to enable them to remain in business and the government should be health insurance for these ICT businesspersons in the event of injuries, fraud and natural catastrophe.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship; ICT; Development; Business; Entrepreneur.

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been, in a relatively limited period, one of the fundamental foundation blocks of contemporary society. Many countries already see ICT learning and mastering essential ICT skills and principles as part of core schooling, including reading, writing, and numeracy. Data and Networking Systems (ICTs) are computer devices used for retrieval and recovery (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman, & Zuwom 2020; Oladimeji, 2018). Design is partially defined by the potential to create a synergistic relationship between scientific advances and human values. The accelerated pace at which ICT has developed since the mid-twentieth century, the proliferation and pervasiveness of ICT, has provided them a significant position in growth and globalization (Nwagwu, 2006). ICTs have a

major effect on all fields of human life in the 21st century (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman, Zuwo, 2020; Awobamise & Jarrar, 2019; Cunningham & Ekenberg, 2016; Ngozi, 2012; Ejeh et al. n.d.).

Information and communication technology (ICT) have been growing vast since the introduction of the internet. The internet helps send, share, or transfer information and data over different internet protocols (IP) in a network to serve billion of users worldwide (Zorayda, 2000). Local entrepreneurship is a very common and important practice in the rural and urban areas of Nigeria, but most common in the rural areas. Considering how everyday businesses go on in most rural areas that are rich in agricultural produces but the people living there still have low standards of living. One begins to wonder why despite the agriculture growth in rural areas, the standard of living is still low. The question that comes to the mind is what can be done to help gain a better standard of living and generate profit for rural settlers? What can be of help in promoting local entrepreneurship? It makes one conclude how ICT can help promote local entrepreneurship in rural areas and help enrich the country's local culture, appreciate the work and produce of the rural areas (Ejeh et al. n.d.).

Entrepreneurship is derived from the French word entrepreneur, which means to initiate or take action. The French used it to describe contractors holding projects like roads and bridges (Musa, 2010; Umeano, 2012). William, et al., (as cited in Umeano, 2012) saw Entrepreneurship as accepting the risk of starting and running a business. They noted that it is the ability and willingness of an individual to create and build something that is virtually none existing (Suleiman & Magaji, 2017).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) consists of a broad range of technical tools and services used to develop, archive, interact, disseminate, and handle information. Enhanced exposure and skills to such innovations are changing the country's economies by creativity in the development and distribution of resources and producing new entrepreneurs (Jorgenson & Vu, 2005). This ICT-driven entrepreneurship is the capacity to develop and accelerate an ICT-based market strategy that uses such innovations to manufacture and distribute products and services (Koellinger, 2005). The Internet has been described as one of the main generators of entrepreneurship (Castells, 2011; Gyaase & Asante, 2014; Iwu & Nzeako, 2012; Jainaba & Kah, 2008; Suleiman, & Zuwo, 2020, Okiyi, et al., 2019; Jarrar, et al., 2020; Awobamise, 2018).

The ability of information and communication technology (ICTs) to change societies and economies has been demonstrated in the literature. The expectation that ICT will play a transformative role is more evident in Africa. Africa, the last frontier of development and known as the poorest continent, has begun to look at ICT as a magic bullet to solve its developmental problems. A recent publication in 2007 by the Africa Capacity Building Foundation argued that there is a high degree of interest in technology solutions to critical growth problems in Africa, which raises the need to accelerate the penetration and deployment of technology on the continent,

especially in the public sector. Technology helps to increase the efficiency and quality of public institutions by providing an enabling environment for the region to increase its competitiveness (Jainaba & Kah, 2008; Cunningham et al. 2016; Suleiman & Zuwo, 2020).

Iwu and Ike (2009) described ICT as the collection, processing, and delivery of a speech, practical; textual, and numerical knowledge through a microelectronic combination of computing and telecommunications. ICT is essentially the use of computer-based information and communication technologies to collect, store, and transfer data. It explains exciting and innovative ways to provide students with global access to information, learning, and support (Iwu & Nzeako 2012). It is a general term that covers all communication devices or applications, including, but not limited to, radio, television, cellular phones, computer network, hardware, software, electronic mail, fax, satellite systems, as well as the various services and applications associated with them. The field of education has been affected by ICT, which has undoubtedly had an impact on teaching and learning. ICTs can improve, enhance, and expand capabilities, inspire and educate pupils, and help connect school interactions to work practices. It also creates economic viability for future employees, as well as strengthening and helping schools to change. Consequently, entrepreneurship education is needed to ensure this (Dawodu, 2005; Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman & Zuwo, 2020).

The Concepts

Entrepreneurship can be defined as a privatization process to turn a company into a venture or to increase and diversify assets or business units with high growth potential. Entrepreneurship is a topic that dominates the world's education circles from the late twentieth century (Ngozi 2012; Tavakoli 2013). Entrepreneurship literature analysis shows that this concept was initially established in economic theory by economists and later reached schools and other scientific theories. Canutillo, who coined the term entrepreneurship, knows needs to know entrepreneur as a venture person who buys goods at a specified cost and sells goods at an undisclosed price. Knows the entrepreneur as the planner and the integrator of the variables of output, but does not find the unique features. In other words, a person who incorporates factors of production (land, labor, and capital) into production, business, or services is called an "entrepreneur" and his job is called an "entrepreneur" (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012; Suleiman & Zuwo, 2020; Cunningham et al. 2016; Tavakoli, 2013).

The partnership between ICT entrepreneurship and small business growth has stimulated research issues in the creation of entrepreneurship and, in particular, the idea of ICT entrepreneurship has drawn a great deal of research attention over a decade. A variety of scholars in the world of business have concluded that the growth of entrepreneurship may lead to small business success through the skills it allows to grow inside the company (Morgan and Sanchez, 2008 in Amue et al, 2013; Tamil & Bartus, 2006). In reality, ensuring the performance of organizations can be

seen as the primary aim of small business growth initiatives in entrepreneurial firms most research on the partnership between ICT entrepreneurship growth and small business creation remains far from being thoroughly clarified. The research of Migisha (2011) suggests that ICT is a medium for growth, but that it can only flourish if small tech start-ups expand and generate new employment by creativity, and that technology is not the only problem, but also entrepreneurship. The opinions of Migisha (2011) face very contradictory observations and claims in the literature (e.g. Adeniyi-kie, 2004; Jackson & Markfish, 2010; Marchese & Polter, 2010). Again, Kola-Ogunlade (2014) suggests that the Web can radically transform the way citizens find and navigate resources (Igwe & Abiye 2014; Awobamise et al., 2020; Awobamise & Jarrar, 2019; Awobamise, 2014).

Again, Kola-Ogunlade (2014) suggests that the Web can radically transform the way citizens find and navigate resources. Eduardo (2006) suggests that google.com is one of the effective tales of young businesspersons leveraging ICT expertise. Kofi and Anns (2010) claim that the diffusion and implementation of ICT entrepreneurship in Western business organizations may be deemed comparatively more established and developed, although its possible effect on less created countries' market networks still needs to be properly stimulated, re-engineered and re-evaluated. The study, therefore, examines the development of ICT entrepreneurship and small business innovation in Nigeria (John et al. 2014), (Jainaba & Kah, 2008).

Increased awareness and enormous potential of ICT entrepreneurship, only very few are taking advantage of and taking advantage of its benefits. "The goals are thus threefold; firstly, we are aiming at fields of ICT development in the sense of Nigeria. Third, we are creating a metric of creativity for the ICT entrepreneurship market. Third, we assess the predictive validity of small business innovation on the likelihood of supporting the development of ICT entrepreneurship. Proposals are created to direct potential work and to address the consequences for development at the corporate and public policy levels" (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; John et al. 2014).

Entrepreneurship

The concept of entrepreneurship was first established in the 1700s, and the meaning has evolved ever since. Many simply equate it with starting one's own business. Most economists believe it is more than that. To some economists, the entrepreneur is one who is willing to bear the risk of a new venture if there is a significant chance for profit. Others emphasize the entrepreneur's role as an innovator who markets his innovation. Still, other economists say that entrepreneurs develop new goods or processes that the market demands and are not currently being supplied. Most economists today agree that entrepreneurship is a necessary ingredient for stimulating economic growth and employment opportunities in all societies. In the developing world, successful small businesses are the primary engines of job creation, income growth, and poverty reduction. Therefore, government support for entrepreneurship is a crucial strategy for economic development (Suleiman & Zuwo,

2020; Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo, 2017).

Orthodox economics has largely ignored the crucial role that the entrepreneur plays in the development of industry and the growth of new markets. This has been especially the case, until recently, in development economics, which appeared to concentrate on macro-economic research and less on microeconomics as a human-driven operation. Entrepreneurship, though, is seen as a crucial contextual part of a variety of economic growth frameworks that understand the complexity of incomplete knowledge (Knight, 1921; Mises, 1966; Kirzner, 1979; Casson, 1982; Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; Duncombe 1999). Drucker (1983) defines an entrepreneur as someone who manages development functions together and shares the burden or insecurity of spending his finite capital in business projects. By doing so, it incorporates the administrative roles of arranging, scheduling, hiring, monitoring, and handling the company. Odusina (1975) sees Entrepreneurship as a mechanism. Usage of usable resources of some way in a transparent and free-market system for the sole purpose of generating income. Entrepreneurs have been defined in a variety of different forms:

- As a fulfillment of a solely functional economic position by planning and distribution of capital within a business setting marked by instability (Casson, 1982).
- As imaginative and inventive prime movers, push the economy forward through productivity by technological and administrative advancement and the creation of modern technologies (Schumpeter, 1943; Williamson, 1983). Entrepreneurs are seen to embody special qualities, distinct from those of managers or owners, which lead to the formation of new products and services, the exploitation of emerging businesses, and greater economic efficiency (Suleiman & B/Zuwo, 2020; Duncombe 1999).
- As an investment hunter (Knight, 1921; Mises, 1966; Kirzner, 1979). We find the capitalist to be essentially a profit-seeking person whose efforts may not generally contribute to economic growth and do not lead to greater productivity in the distribution of capital (Suleiman & B/Zuwo, 2020; Duncombe 1999).

Entrepreneurship has often been identified with a collection of generally optimistic, though primarily inherent, human characteristics that characterize a specific category of person. Can include creativity, enthusiasm, and tolerance to fresh concepts, diligent work, commitment into the future, desire to conserve and spend, leadership, acknowledgment of threats, and selfishness or greed (Grindle, 1989; McClelland, 1976). Theoretical theories for entrepreneurship appear to imply that entrepreneurs are born and not produced and that the financial, economic, and cultural forces that occur inside and within cultures are sometimes not deemed significant. Nevertheless, work in industrialized and developing countries indicates a broad variety of motivating variables that motivate a large range of individuals, from a broad range of

social, economic, and educational backgrounds, to become self-employed/small business owners. (The Storey, 1990; Duncombe 1999).

The position of an entrepreneur, whether creative, profit-seeking, or bureaucratic, would be essential to the collection and usage of knowledge. The entrepreneur will be at the center of the 'enterprise-specific' set of information networks. The entrepreneur must perform the task of finding and defining potential business opportunities; monitoring and organizing reports on the distribution and effective usage of resources; and gathering and utilizing knowledge on new product, process, and management technologies (Duncombe 1999).

Entrepreneurship is characterized as anticipation of benefit from the use of resources (Schumpeter 1934; Hayek 1945; Kirzner 1973, Casson 1982, Shane 2003). The entrepreneur can use tools such as financial aid, low-interest loans, or government funding to operate their company. Law and Macmillan (1998) define entrepreneurship as the creation of a new business venture, which means an entrepreneurial effort at the source of a person to start a business. Krueger et al, (2000) said that entrepreneurial intent is very significant because it is the primary predictor of future entrepreneurial behavior. The entrepreneurship aim is very critical for the growth of entrepreneurship (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman & B/Zuwo, 2020; John et al. 2014).

Entrepreneurs in Nigeria in the early years usually begin their business ventures in small capital, low value-added, and it takes time to set up a business. This type of entrepreneurs needs to collect money, a source of a better place, deal with suppliers and other intermediaries, manpower problems, and other relevant issues while setting up their enterprise (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012; John et al. 2014; Garba 2010).

Technology now lets companies save time and money during the start-up phase of e-business. Information and networking systems have allowed today's entrepreneurs to succeed rather than conventional entrepreneurs. Such rising technology enables conventional businessmen to enter ICT entrepreneurship (Cheng & Chang, 2004; Iwu & Nzeako, 2012; Suleiman & B/Zuwo, 2020; John et al. 2014).

The development of ICT entrepreneurship is becoming the order of business days. Reports (e.g. Mzekandaba, 2013; Austins & Tygris 2010; Eduardo 2006; Kollmann, 2006) suggest that ICT entrepreneurship is rapidly relevant and useful; proof of the growth of ICT entrepreneurship can be seen from active entrepreneurs in Western countries such as the United States (Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; John et al. 2014).

Successful companies in the United States include google.com, yahoo.com, Amazon.com, eBay.com, Twitter, Instagram, etc. Google.com is one of the positive examples of young people with ICT expertise who have been interested in ICT entrepreneurship (Eduardo, 2006). Digital trade is much simpler and cost saving

relative to conventional forms of doing business (Marks & Albert 2009). Digital company does not take too much manpower. Technologies play a supporting function in enabling companies to grow quickly and effectively (Kollmann, 2006; John et al. 2014).

ICT entrepreneurship is the creation of new businesses in the Net Economy (Matlay, 2004). The Net Economy has a strong impact on creative market growth focused on the online knowledge and connectivity network. The information society is characterized by rigorous use of information technology and a shift from an industrial to a knowledge-based economy (Evans & Wurster, 1997; John et al. 2014). Kollmann (2006) claims that the knowledge market is moving from conventional economic sectors (production, services, agriculture). Electronic communication networks and the development of IT have generated a modern.

Why ICT Entrepreneurship

Because of the important role, ICT plays in all aspects of our personal and business lives (Muhammad 2015).

The IT entrepreneur is critical to development. For example, in this era of globalization, ICT entrepreneurship allows countries like Nigeria to become producers and creators in the high-value areas of the knowledge economy. ICTs are the infrastructure of the digital global economy (Muhammad 2015). They are what make the global village possible. However, the majority of entrepreneurship learning programs are offered in business and economic institutions and disciplines. ICT entrepreneurial learning is required to address this state of affairs. There must be an entrepreneurship focus on areas that drive change in today's digital world, particularly ICT (Muhammad 2015).

ICT and Development of Entrepreneurial Competencies

Numerous tasks can be achieved more effectively and with better results thanks to the production of ICT. For example, ICT allows it easy to evaluate various decision-making situations. This is why many people assume this ICT should be used as a resource for the growth and creation of entrepreneurship skills. ICT will provide learning experiences, strategic strategy approaches, management resources as well as company preparation programs with the aid of business plan simulators. ICT will also help to build and strengthen connectivity and social networks (Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; Jagodič & Dermol, 2015).

In the last decades, the EU has gradually pushed towards a service-oriented economy focused heavily on the growth and usage of ICT. Governments promote the production of new skills for EU residents as training for addressing the demands of the labor market. By incorporating unique ICT resources, entrepreneurship capabilities may also be encouraged and youth unemployment can. The EU adopted

a resolution "New technologies for modern employment – 2007" in which the European Commission aims to support Member States in the usage of ICT resources to improve overall capabilities in the working community (European Commission, 2007; Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; Jagodič & Dermol, 2015).

Current ICT should be seen as a way of developing ties between business and higher education. It is a significant chance to provide young people with entrepreneurial knowledge and entrepreneurship awareness. This also affects a wide range of stakeholders, not just students – such as faculty, other educational institutions at all stages, corporations, etc. (Hynes & Richardson, 2007). Effective learning should be implemented to achieve continuous improvement in entrepreneurial skills. Educators would also be conscious of instructional approaches that could be updated to satisfy business expectations to provide students with a range of competencies. Of this cause, the only approach seems to be the usage of ICT software (Galloway et al, 2005). Entrepreneurship preparation includes mastering a range of business-related abilities, such as enhancing decision-making capabilities or exposure to knowledge skills and utilizing various ICT resources to build a better workplace (DeFaoite et al, 2003).

Entrepreneurship Development Education in Nigeria

The term entrepreneurship derives from the term "entrepreneur." According to Encyclopedia Americana (1989), the entrepreneur is a businessman who assumes the risk of bringing together the factors of production and receives his reward in the form of profit from the market value of his products. Okeke (2007) describes entrepreneurship as the acquisition and management of a private enterprise and the creation of a small-scale company directed towards the development of products and services to fulfill the needs and desires of customers. Dawodu (2005) indicated that entrepreneurship promotes economic growth, provides employment prospects, replaces conventional markets and boosts innovation, and raises capital production and performance (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; Oladimeji, 2018; Sharma & Jaipur, 2013).

However, on the other side, entrepreneurship skills are specific skills and competencies that will allow a person to effectively undertake and operate an enterprise. Richen and Salagrik (2003) observed that entrepreneurial skills are learned by training that stresses the acquisition and growth of suitable information and skills that will allow a person to optimize the resources around him within the limits of his or her abilities. Entrepreneurship curriculum is thus a concerted initiative directed at the preparation and growth of entrepreneurship awareness, expertise, and capabilities that are important to the management of an economic enterprise (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012; Muhammad, 2015).

Entrepreneurship learning is crucial to us because it is training and education that enables students to develop and use their creativity to initiate responsibilities and

risks. It has social and economic importance. It helps train the adult for college, and more significantly, it offers a job chance to graduates or people who might otherwise go to higher institutions. Onwukwe (2008) correctly identified the value of entrepreneurship education as an education capable of mitigating deprivation within the community and motivating the deprived section of society (Iwu & Nzeako 2012). An instructor who is well educated in business techniques utilizing knowledge and digital technologies would give students the qualities that can be of benefit to them, as well as transform culture for the better. Not just the deteriorating economic fortunes and increasing waves of unemployment can be reduced by entrepreneurship education, but the large emphasis of the policy must be on reorientation towards entrepreneurship education. There needs to be a change from currently entrepreneurship education in our institutions, which is technically as normal, to entrepreneurial spirit/skills creation in institutions (Iwu & Nzeako 2012; Suleiman & B/Zuwo 2020; Oladimeji, 2018; Sharma & Jaipur, 2013).

Nigerian Agencies for Promoting Entrepreneurship Development

Several organizations have been set up in Nigeria to encourage entrepreneurship and self-employment. Some of them are highlighted below:

- 1) National Directorate of Employment (NDE): The Federal Government of Nigeria founded the National Directorate of Employment in 1986 in its efforts to ensure that its people are self-employed. The government expects that this organization would reduce homelessness, which is a restriction on our culture.
- 2) Special Public Works Programme: A system has been set up to recruit-displaced people in the development and renovation of socially beneficial programs.
- 3) National Development for Employment Entrepreneurship Development Programme (DEEP): NDEEDP runs an Entrepreneurship Development system for students of tertiary institutions and former public / private sector employees to allow them to recognize market opportunities. Participants are marked through awareness-raising preparation during the NYSC orientation program. Which does the Start-Your-Own-Business Learning Course accompany? In 2004, 37,687 NYSC participants benefited from the Entrepreneurship Training System, while 15,374 students of tertiary institutions benefited from Start-Your-Own Company Training (NDE, 2004 cited in Onwukwe, 2008)
- 4) Entrepreneurship Development Studies in Universities (EDS): The National Universities Commission has made it compulsory for all students to be subject to university-level entrepreneurship training. Many colleges have centers for entrepreneurship research in place. Several courses are offered to students in their third year of study. Courses are compulsory for all students, regardless of discipline.

- 5) Private Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (PEDP): Some NGOs also provide programs for the growth of entrepreneurship, like the FATE Base in Lagos, which supports market and entrepreneurial creation. It equips young entrepreneurs with the expertise; resources, networking, and funding they need to develop productive companies. It is aimed at young people between 22 and 23 years of age with a university degree. This is a mentoring system as well as a loan assistance scheme for young entrepreneurs.
- 6) Industrial Training Fund (ITF): The Industrial Training Fund was founded by Decree No 47 of 8 October 1971, to foster and facilitate the acquisition of skills in Industry and Commerce to generate a pool of indigenous skilled staff necessary to meet the needs of the economy (ITF Pamphlet).

Role of ICT in Building New Novelties in Entrepreneurship

ICTs are providing new avenues for job creation that could help tackle global unemployment. For instance, the development of the mobile phone applications industry has created new opportunities for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). A firm that provides a digital application to the Apple app store, for example, gains access to over 500 million app store account holders (Muhammad 2015).

Benefits of Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria

There are some possible areas that an Entrepreneur can invest in ICT to develop himself and others in his area to grow because of his impact. The following are the various opportunities for ICT entrepreneurship available to an Entrepreneur according to Sulaiman and Bakin-Zuwo (2017):

1. Rural Saving Mobilization: Establishing community banks is a program to further generate rural resources for economic purposes. Such savings help to improve economic growth in rural areas (Iwu & Nzeako 2012).
2. Business Centre and Internet Cafe: This is an ICT business, which is run by an entrepreneur. In this center, photocopying machines, computers, typewriters, scanners, printers, telephones, and other ICT tools are used to provide services to customers. The entrepreneur employs other people to work for him in the center and change the services with the trend of things based on the customers' requests and demands (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
3. Generation of Employment Opportunities: Both small and medium-sized businesses produce more job prospects than any big companies do. Most people rely on their companies for their work and can employ someone to support them (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).

4. Stimulation of Indigenous Entrepreneurship Development: The knowledge and expertise acquired in small companies assist in the activity and management of big enterprises (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).
5. Internet Travelling Agency: Though this is not common in the rural areas big cities, travelers book, and liaise with national airlines and other airlines operating within the country through the entrepreneur running such a business by making travel arrangements for them. He can provide the service of ticketing and booking of airlines through net provided they are ready to pay (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
6. Computer Technicians: The technicians who service and maintain the equipment are entrepreneurs that are making their living through this service. This is even the cheapest because one does not need much money, rather tools and excellent knowledge of the computer and its parts. They make a lot of money from this because the equipment must have problems and people must call them and they charge as they like and you have to pay because you are not knowledgeable there. The ICT entrepreneurship opportunities are too numerous that one could go on and on to write on them (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
7. Modification of Traditional Industries: The creation of indigenous and local businesses and technology can be accomplished by entrepreneurship education. Countries like Japan, Taiwan, Singapore, South Korea, and so on have made significant improvements in their local and traditional industries through indigenous entrepreneurship education (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).
8. Computer Training Centre: This is one of the roles ICT entrepreneurs is playing by creating jobs for people and educating people who wish to learn ICT or even knowledge-based users. The entrepreneur makes a lot of money in this especially if he has enough staff and students even the facilities for teaching and learning (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).

Problems of Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria

Though many opportunities are available for entrepreneurs, these are not without some limiting factors. Some of these factors are:

1. Tax system: The entrepreneur suffers the problem of multiple taxes, and numerous revenues to pay. These in most cases discourage the entrepreneur from his establishment. It is little or no tax relief for the entrepreneur to encourage him to contribute positively to the economy (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
2. Lack of qualified technicians/repairers: An entrepreneur suffers at times when there is a fault in the ICT tools because some of the technicians are not

specialists in the maintenance of these tools, which delays operations and services. This affects the livelihood of the entrepreneur (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).

3. Lack of mentorship: A mentorship plan for educational programs needs to be implemented so that aspiring companies can benefit from established businesspersons (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
4. Crises and insecurity: Crises or insecurity which are the major issues in the country could cause the entrepreneur everything he has labored for in less than an hour. This is not a healthy development for him. Some states are no go areas now in Nigeria because of bombing and kidnapping that is common with them, and people would not want to invest in these places or be happy that their investment went down the drain in such places. This would affect development in such areas and poverty will be on the increase (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
5. Power failure: ICT entrepreneurs cannot operate without adequate power supply and this is a major challenge because the power supply in the country has been in a coma and is still there. The cost of buying, fueling, and maintaining a standby generator is on the high side (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
6. New technology: The entrepreneur does not have enough money to continue to change the latest technologies being pumped into the market every time. There is always a new one on a weekly or monthly basis (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
7. Cost of facilities: The ICT tools are expensive due to importation costs. This problem makes some interested entrepreneurs to be discouraged because of the money involved in establishing this (Suleiman & Bakin-Zuwo 2017).
8. The short duration of Programs: Most services are limited in length, varying from one week to a few weeks/months. There will be ample room for functional components to be integrated (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).
9. Inadequate funding and capacity: Considering the extent of the issue of youth jobs in Nigeria and the number of possible beneficiaries, further studies are expected to hit a greater number of young people annually (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).
10. Absence of linkages between training agencies and institutions: Most educational institutes have almost no proof of collaborative arrangements between them and growth agencies in the country (Iwu & Nzeako, 2012).

CONCLUSION

By the foregoing, it can be shown that many countries' policy considers entrepreneurship as the underpinnings of their economy's industrialization and therefore promotes entrepreneurship. ICT entrepreneurship, however, still has a significant amount of growth. Entrepreneurship is a prerequisite for the development of technology, and the development of technology is a foundation for entrepreneurship education. Government agencies should develop and strengthen the entrepreneurial background in computer technology, which is communication and information networks, and provide easy access to these networks while developing and developing the use of networks, as well as design and evaluate rules and regulations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Giving regard to the important comments discussed, the following recommendations should be made to boost the ICT Entrepreneurship Development Education quality in Nigeria and thus alleviate poverty among graduates of colleges and universities in Nigeria, as follows:

1. The government and private sectors must establish a core agency to build entrepreneurship, creating investors, and promoting a vast number of entrepreneurs in various economic sectors.
2. Energy shortage should be resolved to ensure companies are remaining in the sector, raising revenue, employing people, and growing poverty in the area.
3. Educators with sufficient experience in the curriculum of entrepreneurship will be provided with compulsory kits to build a small-scale business for ICT issues.
4. Upon graduation, every tertiary graduate student should be allowed to own basic hand and computer tools that match his or her area of expertise for entrepreneurship.
5. Throughout the event of soft loans, the government wants to offer financial support to aid and enable students and other representatives of the public who growing to join the self-reliance market.

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